

ADSORPTION OF LEADS IONS FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION BY SAWDUST WASTES

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ABSTRACT

Sawdust waste was used as a potential adsorption matrix for Pb^{2+} ions removal from aqueous solutions at room temperature. A parameter such as particle size of the adsorbent at acidic pH was studied at room temperature to optimize the desired particle size to be utilized on a commercial scale for the decontamination of effluents using a batch adsorption technique for Pb^{2+} ions. The optimum particle size for Pb^{2+} ions removal was $0.71\mu m$ and the percentage removed at equilibrium condition was 99.1%, which means that Pb^{2+} ions can be effectively removed from aqueous solutions by sawdust waste. The mechanisms for adsorption of Pb^{2+} ions onto sawdust waste involved ion exchange or the formation of hydroxyl complexes. The results obtained could be useful for the application of sawdust waste for heavy metal removal from industrial wastewater.

* Keywords: Adsorption, Pb^{2+} ion, pH, sawdust waste, aqueous solution.

INTRODUCTION

Owing to industrialization in many countries. The levels of industrial pollution have been steadily increasing. Thus the pollution problem of industrial wastewater is becoming more and more serious in the world. Consequently, the treatment of polluted industrial wastewater remain a topic of global concern since wastewater collected for municipalities, communities and industries must ultimately be returned to receiving water or to land. Moreover, contamination of groundwater is today a major concern in the management of water resources (Weder et al., 1991)

Contaminants such as heavy metals are characterized by a wide variety of processes in humans. This is because the presence of heavy metal has a potentially damaging effect on human physiology and other biological systems when the tolerance levels are exceeded (Fatoki et al., 2002)

Many methods of treatment for industrial wastewater have been report in literature (Periasany and Namasivayam, 1995; Dimitrova and Mehandgiev, 1998; Drake et al., 1996; Kumar, 2006; Xu et al., 2005, Hashem, 2007). Amongst these methods are neutralization, precipitation, ion exchange and adsorption. For low concentrations of metal ions in wastewater, the adsorption process is recommended for their removal. The process of adsorption entails the application of an "adsorbent" solid that binds molecules by physical attractive forces, ion exchange, and chemical binding. Further, it is advisable that the adsorbent is available in large quantities, easily regenerable, and cheap. Following the forgoing, activated carbon is widely used as an effective adsorbent in many applications. It is the most commonly used adsorbent in the adsorption process for the treatment of waster (Mckay, 1984)but metal ion removal by adsorption with activated carbon is

relatively expensive. The process for removing metal ions from aqueous solutions by different activated carbon obtained from agricultural by-products has already been published (Orhan and Buyungor, 1993). Due to the high cost of activated carbon and 10-15% loss during regeneration, alternative low cost adsorbents have attracted the attention of several investigators to provide an alternative for the high cost of activated carbon. Although several studies were available explaining the utilization of several low cost adsorbents, most of these works stand at the laboratory level and only a very few cases have been directed implemented in practical applications at the industrial level (Abia et al., 2003).

Agricultural by-products could be heavy metal adsorbents, which could be selective for some metal ions (Al Duri, 1995). Agricultural materials such as banana and orange peels (Annadurai et al., 2002), maize cob, coconut husk fibres (Tan et al., 1993; Babarinde, 2002) nut shells (Demirdas, 2003); soybeans and cottonseed hulls have been evaluated, for their adsorptive properties. These materials have been reported to adsorb different pollutants such as heavy metal ions, dyestuff and other toxic pollutants (El-Geundi, 1997). Refined corn hulls, groundnut husks and rice hulls have also been evaluated for the adsorption of heavy metal ions from wastewater. Research in the use of agricultural by-products (Abia and Asuquo, 2006) has included metal binding studies with *Datura innoxia*, dyed cellulosic materials, wheat and rice bran, oat fiber, sugarcane bagasse, and maize cob to mention a few (El-Geundi, 1997; Al-Duri, Nassar and El-Geundi, 1994).

In this study, lead was chosen because of its environmental significance, which is related to its well known toxicity (Fatoki

et al., 2002) and intensive use in industries such as storage-battery manufacture, printing, pigment manufacturing, petrochemicals fuel combustion and photographic materials (Carson et al., 1986). This is because the assimilation in the human body of relatively small amounts of over a long period of time can lead to malfunctioning of certain organs and chronic toxicity (Fatoki et al., 2002).

Therefore, it is great of great importance to develop a method for lead ion adsorption or removal from water by testing the capabilities of sawdust and the effect of particle size on the percentage of removal of lead.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sawdust waster used for the experiment were obtained from the saw-mill in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state, Nigeria. They were washed with de-ionized waters were then ground with a mechanical grinder. After being ground, the sawdust particles were sieved into two groups: 0.71 μm and 0.85 μm respectively. After that, the sawdust wastes were dried at 100°C to reach a constant weight.

Stock solution of lead (1000 mg/L) was prepared lead nitrate water. The concentration of lead that was prepared from the stock solution and used in the experiment was 10mg/L.

For each set experiment, the pre-treated organic material of a particular particle size was packed in a glass column that was fritted with cotton wool and vertically with the aid of a clamp and a retort stand, 50 ml of synthetic water containing Pb^{2+} ions was introduced and allowed to remain in the packed column for 50 minutes before elution. A duplicate analysis for each sample to track experimental error show capability of reproducing results was carried out.

The residual lead was analyzed by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry using Buck Scientific Model 200A Spectrophotometer, which was equipped with a high sensitivity nebulizer. The adsorbed phase concentration was calculated using the following equation (Nassar, 1997):

$$Q_e = V(C_i - C_f) / W$$

Where C_i is the initial lead concentration in the synthetic; C_f is the final lead concentration in the eluate; W is the weight of adsorbent used and V is volume of solution.

Thereafter, the percentage of lead removed was calculated on the basis of Q_e .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Effect of acidic PH

The adsorption behavior of Pb^{2+} ion was studied in the aqueous phase at acidic PH, which is the principal factor influencing the high adsorptive capacity of Pb^{2+} ion at acidic PH is noted to be due to the decreases in the hydrogen ion concentration as the PH value decreases. Besides, the removal of lead from solutions present several difficulties, mainly due to the fact that a precipitation process is not possible by simple PH regulation of the solution as in the case of polyvalent metal cations (Xu et al., 2006). In this study, Pb^{2+} ion was

effectively adsorbed in the acidic PH range of 4-5, which is similar to the heavy metal ion sorption on agricultural wastes (Rodda et al., 1993). Hashem (2007) found that the solution increased.

Effect of adsorbent size.

The particle size of adsorbent employed was found to influence the efficiency of the adsorption process (Table 1). This parameter was optimized in conjunction with the other optimized parameter at room temperature (10 mg/l lead at a HP = 4-5 by passing Pb^{2+} ion in aqueous solution through different particle sizes of sawdust waters. The optimum particle size for Pb^{2+} ions removal was 0.71 μ m and the percentage removed at equilibrium condition was 99.1%, which means that Pb^{2+} ions can be effectively removed from aqueous solutions by sawdust waste. The mechanisms for adsorption of Pb^{2+} ions onto sawdust waste involved ion exchange or the formation of hydroxyl complexes. Similarly, Dimitrova and Mehandgiev (1998) considered that the observed effect is connected with the re-dislodgement of calcium from such wastes into the solution and therefore the sites for the sorption of Pb^{2+} ion are set free. However, the adsorption of metal ion on agricultural by-products may involve metal interactions (Kumar, 2006) or coordination to functional group present in natural proteins, lipids, and carbohydrates positioned on cell walls (Drake et al., 1996).

Table 1: Effect of particle size of adsorbent on the percentage of lead removed from the synthetic waste water

Organic Waste	Particle Size (mm)	% Pb
Wood	0.710	99.1
Wood Flour	0.850	97.4

CONCLUSIONS

Sawdust wastes are adsorbents of great potential and had proven to be an appropriate adsorbent for lead removal from aqueous solutions at acidic PH. Based on the experimental conditions, it is therefore concluded that removal of Pb^{2+} ion from their aqueous solutions at acidic PH using sawdust wastes shows a new trend for liquid wastes treatment for the benefit of environmental pollution control

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